

ASSESSMENT OF THE EXTENT OF RICE SMALL-HOLDER FARMERS' PRODUCTIVITY AND THEIR PERCEPTIONS OF THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL EXTENSION SERVICES IN BAUCHI STATE, NIGERIA

Muhammad, A.T.^{*1}, F. Dutse,¹ S.K. Haruna,² and Alabi, S.I. ¹

¹Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development, Faculty of Agriculture, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria.

²National Agricultural Extension and Research Liaison Services (NAERLS) Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria.

Corresponding author's email: Turakikatagum01@gmail.com (+2347062215143)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.70118/ajaas.02025050502.02>

ABSTRACT

The productivity of small-holder farmers of rice and their perceptions of agricultural extension agents are vital for food security and extension service effectiveness. This research examines respondents' socio-economic and institutional characteristics, the productivity levels of rice small-holders, and their views on the role of agricultural extension services in Bauchi State, Nigeria. Using a multistage sampling procedure, 298 respondents were selected, and primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized to analyse the data. Findings indicated that the average age of rice farmers was 42 years, with a significant majority (82.6%) being married. It was revealed that more than half (56.0%) of the rice farmers achieved a productivity level exceeding 2.0, indicating that they earned twice their total revenue. Regarding perceptions, a substantial majority (86.6%) viewed agricultural extension services positively in terms of enhancing rice productivity. The study concluded that the high productivity levels among farmers are a positive indicator for the rice sector in the state. Additionally, the favourable perceptions of extension services are likely linked to farmers' access to physical extension services, which positively affect their attitudes. It is recommended that both private and public extension services focus on disseminating best practices in rice farming to sustain rice productivity and enhance the effectiveness of extension services.

Keywords: Productivity, Perception, Rice, Extent, Bauchi State.

INTRODUCTION

Rice is a fundamental food source for more than half of the world's population and plays a vital role in ensuring food security, alleviating poverty, and fostering economic growth, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa,

including Nigeria (FAO, 2021). In Nigeria, rice is the most widely consumed grain, and its demand is rapidly increasing due to population growth, urban migration, and evolving dietary preferences (MUHAMMAD and AJANI 2025).

Although Nigeria ranks among Africa's largest rice producers, it still significantly depends on imports to satisfy domestic needs, highlighting the necessity to enhance local production, particularly by smallholder farmers who account for over 80% of the country's rice output (World Bank, 2020).

Smallholder rice producers in Nigeria face numerous obstacles, such as limited access to improved seed varieties, insufficient irrigation infrastructures, poor access to credit, and low uptake of modern agricultural techniques (Olagunju *et al.*, 2020). These existing challenges have resulted in low productivity levels in Nigeria, with the average rice yield at around 2.2 tons per hectare, which is notably below the global average of 4.5 tons per hectare (FAO, 2021). To tackle these issues, it is crucial to enhance agricultural extension services that play a significant role in disseminating knowledge, technologies, and best practices to farmers. Doing so can boost productivity and improve livelihoods (Norton and Alwang, 2020).

By acting as a liaison between farmers and research organizations, agricultural extension services help spread innovations and encourage environmentally friendly farming methods (Davis *et al.*, 2020). Non-governmental organizations (NGOs), government agencies, and private sector players are the main providers of extension services in Nigeria. However, a low ratio of extension agents to farmers, poor infrastructure, and inadequate resources have all constrained the efficiency of these programs (Adebayo *et al.*, 2020). Nigeria, for example, has one extension worker for every 10,000 farmers, which is far less than the suggested ratio of 1:500, according to the World Bank (2020). This circumstance

stresses the necessity of evaluating the function and influence of extension services on the productivity of smallholder rice farmers as well as their view of these services in the study area.

Bauchi State, located in north-eastern Nigeria, ranks among the country's key rice-producing regions due to its favourable conditions for rice farming (NBS, 2021). Smallholder farmers in the area are crucial to rice production, but they face challenges akin to those experienced by farmers in other regions of Nigeria. It is important to comprehend their productivity levels and views on agricultural extension services to create focused strategies that will boost rice production and enhance the livelihoods of individuals in the state.

Recent studies highlight the importance of farmers' perceptions in influencing the adoption of agricultural innovations and the effectiveness of extension services (Ajayi and Mbah, 2021). However, there is a lack of empirical research focused on the specific context of Bauchi State, which underscores the necessity of this study. To address this gap, it is important to gain insights into the productivity of smallholder rice farmers and their perceptions of the role of extension services.

This study aims to achieve the following research objectives: identify the socioeconomic and institutional characteristics of the respondents, examine the level of rice productivity among smallholder farmers, and assess their perceptions of how agricultural extension services impact rice productivity in the study area.

2.0. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Study Area

Bauchi State has an estimated population of around 8,308,800 people, with a growth rate of 3.2% per year, according to the

National Population Census conducted in borders with seven other states; to the north, 2006. It is located between latitudes 9°30' it adjoins the Kano and Jigawa States, while and 10°48' north of the equator, and the Taraba and Plateau States lie south. To longitudes 8°45' and 15°0' east of the the east, it is bordered by Gombe and Yobe, Greenwich Meridian. The state receives and to the west, it neighbours Kaduna State. annual rainfall that varies between 700 mm Covering a total land area of 49,259 square and 1,300 mm. In the savannah region, the kilometres, Bauchi State constitutes about rainy season begins in May and concludes 5.3% of Nigeria's landmass (Toro and in October, with rainfall variability Mustapha 2023). The major crops increasing as one moves north. Relative cultivated in the state include rice, maize, humidity ranges from about 12% in millet, cowpea, guinea corn, and February to approximately 68% in August. groundnut. The prominent livestock raised Bauchi State is divided into two main here include sheep, goats, cattle, domestic vegetation zones: the Sudan Savannah and poultry, and guinea fowl. (Federal Republic the Sahel Savannah. The state shares its of Nigeria: Report 2019).

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing the study area.

2.2. Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A multistage sampling procedure was employed in this study. In the first stage, two (2) Local Government Areas (Zaki and Jama'are) in Bauchi state were purposively selected because of its predominance of rice production in the floodplain wetland of Hadejia-Jama'are rivers in Northern

Nigeria, making them predominantly rice farming communities (Tanko, 2013). In the second stage, a random sampling technique such as balloting was used to select five (5) communities each from the (2) two Local Government Areas making a total of 10 communities. The lists of rice small-holder farmers in the (2) two Local Government Areas were obtained from the Bauchi State

Agricultural Development Program (BSADP) office in the State which formed the sample frame of 1,168 rice farmers for the study and the sample size was randomly selected representing 25.5% of the sample frame. The sample size was calculated using the Taro Yamane formula. The formula is given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where:

n = sample size, N = total population, 1 = statistical constant, e = the assumed error of margin or significance level which is taken as 0.05 i.e. 95% confidence level.

2.3. Method of Data Collection

Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered to farmers through the Kobocollect system. Information collected includes; The information collected included the socioeconomic characteristics of rice small-holders, the level of rice small-holder farmers’ productivity and their perceptions of the roles of Agricultural extension services on rice productivity in the study area. Two enumerators were used for this exercise which were supervised by the researcher.

2.4. Analytical Techniques

Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to summarize and achieve objectives i and ii and **objective iii)** the level of small-holder farmers’ rice productivity was achieved using descriptive statistics and the productivity index. The mean was generated and categorized rice farmers’ level of

productivity as 0.00-0.40 = very low, 0.41-1.00 = low, 1.01-1.50 = medium, 1.51-2.00 = high, and greater than 2.00 = very high productivity. This productivity category was adopted from the work of Coelli (1996), where he conceptualizes productivity as the ratio of total revenue (that is, production of quantity produced and the unit price) and the total input cost.

The higher the ratio, the more productive the farmers are and the more efficient they are in the use of allocation factors of production.

3.0. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Socioeconomic and institutional characteristics of rice farmers

The results in Table 1 indicate that a significant proportion (32.6%) of rice farmers are within the age range of 40 to 49 years, with a mean age of 42 years. This suggests that the production of rice in the study area is largely undertaken by active individuals who have the energy to maximize the potential of the rice sub-sector. This finding aligns with Filli *et al.* (2023), who reported that 95% of rice producers in Taraba State are predominantly in their prime working age.

Furthermore, the findings reveal that 36.6% of the rice farmers had received secondary education, while only 22% possessed tertiary education. This suggests that, due to the importance of education in understanding new agricultural practices and services, rice farmers in the study area possess a solid educational background. This enables them to comprehend and make informed decisions about adopting or rejecting the available agricultural practices and services. This is consistent with the work of Rasaki *et al.* (2020), which found that most rice farmers in Taraba State have

some form of formal education. The results also indicate that a majority (57.4%) of rice farmers cultivate land ranging from 1 to 2 hectares, with an average farm size of 1.7 hectares. The findings suggest that the rice farmers in the study area are mainly small-scale cultivators who face various production constraints, resulting in a gap in rice production. This conclusion is consistent with research by Mohammed *et al.* (2023), which found that most wheat farmers in Jigawa State also operate on farms smaller than 1 hectare. Furthermore, the respondents demonstrated significant experience in rice farming, with nearly half (47.3%) having between 6 to 10 years of farming experience, and the average experience being 7.1 years. This suggests that many respondents possess substantial experience in rice farming, which could be advantageous for adapting to evolving practices and enhancing productivity. This observation corresponds with findings by Nwaobiala and Uchechi (2016), who noted that farmers in Abia State also exhibited significant years of farming experience.

The results further revealed that a large proportion (41.2%) of farmers have received credit ranging from N400,001 to N500,000, with a mean amount of N342,606.06. This indicates that rice farmers in Bauchi State have access to a considerable amount of credit, allowing them to expand their rice farms and potentially increase their productivity. Moreover, it was found that the majority (80.2%) of rice farmers are members of a cooperative society. This indicates that most farmers are part of a group, which is advantageous for accessing credit, information, and services that could enhance their rice production. Additionally, more than half (51.0%) of the rice farmers benefit from agricultural subsidies provided by the government and non-governmental organizations. This implies that rice farmers in the state can produce rice at a lower cost, thereby increasing their profit potential.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents according to their Socioeconomic and institutional Characteristics Variables Age 18-

	29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60 above	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Std.dev.
						2	8.1		
						5	28.		
						8	5	42	9.967
						5	32.		
						9	6		
Level of education						7	26.		
Tertiary						7	22.		
Secondary						8	27.		
Primary						9	36.		
Non-formal						3	6		
Farm size						6	17		
1-2 3-4 5 above						17	22.	1.7	1.187
Farming experience						1	4		
1-5 6-10 11-15 16-20						11	39.		
20 above						7	3		
Amount of credit received.						10	24.		
<3000-200000						3	3	7.1	5.858
200001-300000						14	47.		
300001-400000						1	3		
400001-500000						17	5.7		
500000 above						6	2.0		
Agricultural subsidies						11	37.		
Yes No						5	30.		
						1	9		
						1	9.7		
						6	12.	342606.06	188501.462
						2	1		
						0	41.		
						5	21.0		
						2	49		
Source: Field survey, 2024						14			
						6			

3.4. Level of Small-holder Farmer’s Rice Productivity The results shown in Table 2 indicate that more than half (56.0%) of rice farmers experienced very high productivity levels during the last growing season, marked by a productivity ratio greater than 2.0. This finding aligns with the study by Lawal et al. (2023), which reveals that smallholder rice farmers who receive subsidized inputs, enhanced seed varieties, and extension services, often provided through initiatives like the Anchor Borrowers' Program, can achieve yields that are at least twice the costs of their inputs.

This relationship highlights the crucial role that access to resources and education plays in fostering agricultural success. Programs that offer financial assistance and learning opportunities allow farmers to adopt better farming techniques and invest in high-

quality inputs, ultimately leading to improved yields. The positive results noted in this scenario suggest a model that could be applied in other areas, underscoring the contributions of both governmental and non-governmental organizations in enhancing agricultural productivity.

On the other hand, farmers with productivity ratios below 2.0, as observed by Eze et al. (2023), encounter significant obstacles that hinder their agricultural potential. Issues such as limited credit access, insufficient irrigation systems, and considerable post-harvest losses greatly weaken their effectiveness. In the absence of targeted measures to tackle these challenges, these farmers risk remaining trapped in a low productivity cycle, which not only threatens their livelihoods but also endangers food security in Northern Nigeria.

Table 2: Distribution of rice farmers according to their level of rice productivity

Level of productivity	Productivity category	Frequency	Percentage
Very low		90	8.10
Low		23	
Medium	0.00-0.40	167	30.2
High	1.01-1.50		3.4
Very high	1.51-2.00		7.7
	>2.00		56.0
Inputtype	Low range	Medium range	Highrange
Seeds (kg/ha)	<12-30	31 - 50	e
Fertilizer (50kg/bag)	<1-2	3-5	>51 >6
Agrochemicals(litres)	<5	6-10	>10
Farm size(ha)	1 – 1.5	1.6 - 2	> 2
Annual Labour=(N)	< 185,000	185,000 – 250,000	>250,000
Yield (Tons)	< 2	2 - 3.5	>3.5

3.5. Perceptions of Rice Small-holder Farmers of the Role of Agricultural Extension Services on Rice Productivity

Table 3 presents a comprehensive analysis of respondents' perceptions of the role of agricultural extension services on productivity among rice farmers. The data indicates a strong consensus among respondents, reflected in a mean score of 1.43 for the critical function of disseminating information on recommended agricultural practices. This emphasizes the significance of effective communication in promoting best practices among farmers.

Additionally, the study identified several other vital roles acknowledged by the participants. These include conducting farmer training sessions, which received a mean score of 2.13, and organizing and encouraging the formation of cooperatives or groups, scoring 2.11. The connection of farmers to agro-input dealers was highlighted with a mean score of 2.28 while linking farmers to credit institutions received a score of 2.27. Providing access to essential farm services scored 2.23, promoting the adoption of improved agricultural technologies achieved a score of 2.01, and involving farmers in program or project planning garnered a mean score of 2.36.

These findings collectively illustrate the crucial role that respondents ascribe to various agricultural extension services in bolstering rice production. The favorable perceptions are further substantiated by the significant percentage of respondents, 86.6%, who expressed a positive outlook toward the extension services they receive. This favorable sentiment culminated in a perception index ranging from 0.71 to 1.00, indicating a robust acknowledgement of the importance of these services in not only enhancing productivity but also contributing to the overall success of rice farming.

Furthermore, these results align with the conclusions of Maulu *et al.* (2021), who noted that farmers recognize extension services as effective instruments for improving productivity in rice cultivation. The insights derived from this study reinforce the necessity of investing in agricultural extension services, as they are integral to empowering farmers and advancing agricultural development within the study area. Such initiatives could significantly enhance both the economic viability and sustainability of rice farming, thereby supporting food security and rural development in the region.

Table 3: Distribution of rice farmers according to their perception of the role of agricultural extension services on their productivity

Perceptions of the Role of Extension Services	Score	Mean score	Remark
Disseminates information to farmers on recommended practices, education and enlightenment. 457		1.43	Strongly Agree
Conduct farmer's training - workshops, demonstrations, field days. 636		2.13	Agree
Organizing and encouraging farmers to form cooperatives/groups 629		2.11	Agree
Link farmers to agro-input dealers – agrochemical, fertilizer. 680		2.28	Agree
Link farmers to credit institutions – Banks, farmuptakers. 679		2.27	Agree
Link farmers to farm services – Farm equipment hire. 665		2.23	Agree
Promote Farmer's adoption of improved technologies 559		2.01	Agree
Involve and mobilize farmers in program/project planning/implementation or leadership training. 706		2.36	Agree
Types of Perception Index		Frequency	Percentage
Negative	0.00-0.50	2	0.6
Neutral	0.51-0.70	38	12.8
Positive	0.71-1.00	258	86.6

Note: 1 = strongly agree, 2 = agree, 3 = undecided, 4 = disagree, 5 = strongly disagree

4.0. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

According to the outcomes of these discoveries, it was concluded that a significant number of smallholder rice farmers achieve very high productivity, largely due to access to subsidized inputs and effective agricultural extension services. Farmers acknowledge the crucial role of extension services in increasing their rice yields and productivity by providing information sharing, training, and access to financing, highlighting their essential contribution to enhancing productivity and

improving farmer livelihoods. Consequently, it is suggested that; Farmers acknowledge the crucial role of extension services in increasing their rice yields and productivity by providing information sharing, training, and access to financing, highlighting their essential contribution to enhancing productivity and improving farmer livelihoods. Consequently, it is suggested that;

- i. Agricultural agencies, public and private extension services and government bodies should improve the

effectiveness and outreach of agricultural extension services by utilizing modern communication tools.

ii. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs), agricultural cooperatives, and government programs should implement targeted interventions for farmers with productivity ratios below 2.0 to address challenges such as access to credit and post-harvest losses.

iii. Agricultural associations, stakeholders, extension agents and local governments should encourage the establishment of farmer cooperatives to

strengthen bargaining power and facilitate resource sharing.

iv. Agricultural training institutions and NGOs should offer additional workshops focused on modern agricultural practices and business skills to empower farmers.

v. Farmers' associations, input suppliers, and financial institutions should build partnerships to improve access to essential resources.

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